

Perceptions and Experiences of the Students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School Towards Herbal Medicine

Ranyiza H. Aradji^{1*}, Jheeda H. Jalilul², Fattema Ye'eza I. Maung³, Anirhawa K. Panasang⁴, Altamir A. Salamuddin⁵

Authors Information:

¹⁻⁵Mindanao State University–Sulu, Senior High School, Philippines.

Correspondence:

ranyizaaradji@gmail.com

Article History:

Date Received: May 2, 2026

Date Revised: May 9, 2026

Date Accepted: May 10, 2026

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20248501>

Document ID: 2026IJROMS0061

Recommended Citation:

Aradji, R. H., Jalilul, J. H., Maung, F. Y. I., Panasang, A. K., & Salamuddin, A. A. (2026). Perceptions and Experiences of the Students at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School Towards Herbal Medicine. *International Journal of Research on Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(4), 219–226. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20248501>

Abstract. Herbal medicine continues to play an important role in Filipino culture because of its accessibility, affordability, and traditional value. Despite the increasing use of modern medicine, many students still rely on herbal remedies for common illnesses. However, limited studies have explored the perceptions and experiences of Senior High School students toward herbal medicine, particularly in Mindanao State University–Sulu. This quantitative descriptive-comparative study aimed to determine the level of knowledge, commonly used herbal medicines, and significant differences in students' perceptions when grouped according to age, gender, and academic strand. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to select 157 respondents from the Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic Strand (GAS). Data were collected using an adapted survey questionnaire and analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, Mann–Whitney U test, and Kruskal–Wallis H test. Findings revealed that student level of knowledge and positive perceptions toward herbal medicine, with a grand weighted mean of 3.63. Lagundi, guava leaves, bawang, and sambong were identified as the most commonly used herbal medicines among respondents. Statistical findings further revealed that there were no significant differences in perceptions when respondents were grouped according to age, gender, and academic strand. The results suggest that students' knowledge and use of herbal medicine are influenced more by cultural traditions, family practices, and community beliefs than by demographic factors. The study recommends promoting evidence-based and culturally sensitive education regarding herbal medicine to encourage safe and responsible use among students.

Keywords: Awareness; Herbal medicine; Perceptions; Senior high school students; Traditional medicine

Introduction

Herbal medicine has long been part of human healthcare and continues to play a significant role in many cultures worldwide. In the Philippines, the use of medicinal plants remains common because herbal remedies are affordable, accessible, and deeply rooted in cultural traditions. Many Filipino families continue to rely on locally available plants to treat common illnesses and maintain health. These practices are often passed from one generation to another, contributing to the continued relevance of traditional medicine despite the widespread availability of modern pharmaceutical products.

Among young people, particularly students, the use of herbal medicine continues to exist alongside modern healthcare practices. Previous studies revealed that Filipino students generally possess positive perceptions toward herbal medicine due to family influence, cultural exposure, accessibility, and personal experiences. Adlaon and Elandag (2022) found that communities in Bucas Grande Island possessed substantial knowledge regarding traditional medicine, although the actual utilization of herbal remedies varied. Similarly, Madale and Salic-Hairulla (2024) reported that students from MSU–Iligan Institute of Technology demonstrated positive attitudes toward herbal plants such as malunggay, guava, and calamansi. Other studies also emphasized the importance of preserving indigenous knowledge and promoting the responsible use of herbal medicine among younger generations.

Although previous studies explored the awareness and utilization of herbal medicine among university students, indigenous communities, and rural populations in the Philippines, limited research has focused specifically on Senior High School students in Mindanao State University–Sulu. Furthermore, there is insufficient evidence regarding whether demographic variables such as age, gender, and academic strand significantly influence students' perceptions and experiences toward herbal medicine. This gap highlights the need for further investigation among younger populations who continue to be exposed to both traditional and modern healthcare practices.

This study is anchored on the Health Belief Model (HBM), which explains that individuals' beliefs, experiences, and perceived benefits influence their health-related behaviors. Using this framework, the study aimed to determine the perceptions and experiences of Senior High School students at Mindanao State University–Sulu toward herbal medicine and examine whether demographic factors significantly influence these perceptions. The findings of this study may contribute to the preservation of indigenous knowledge, promote evidence-based use of herbal medicine, and support the development of culturally sensitive health education programs among students.

Research Questions

This study aims to explore the perceptions and experiences of students at Mindanao State University – Sulu, Senior High School towards herbal medicine,

Specifically seeking to answer the following questions;

1. What is the level of knowledge of Senior High School students toward Herbal Medicine?
2. What are the herbal medicine commonly used by the students in MSU Sulu?
3. Is there significance difference on the perceptions of SHS students towards Herbal Medicine when data are grouped according to their age, gender, and strand?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The investigation is on the awareness and the practice of Herbal Medicine in the context of Grade 11 students of MSU–Sulu Senior High School in the school year 2025–2026.

The research is confined to the survey participants; it does not cover other types of traditional healing methods or contemporary medical interventions. It also excludes laboratory analysis and clinical evaluation of herbal preparations.

Literature Review

Cultural and Community Foundations of Herbal Medicine Use

Herbal medicine use in the Philippines is strongly rooted in cultural traditions and indigenous knowledge systems. Across various regions, studies consistently show that medicinal plants remain an integral part of community health practices. For instance, Adlaon and Elandag (2022) found that communities in Bucas Grande Island possess substantial knowledge of traditional medicine, reflecting long-standing reliance on natural remedies. This pattern is also evident in indigenous groups, where Andalan et al. (2024) documented the continued use of medicinal and ritual plants among communities in Benguet. Similarly, Panergo et al. (2024) reported that rural communities in Cagayan maintain ethnobotanical practices passed through generations, reinforcing the role of cultural transmission in sustaining herbal medicine use. In a broader national context, Meñiza et al. (2024) identified more than 500 medicinal plants documented in Mindanao, indicating the extensive ethnobotanical knowledge across Philippine regions. Together, these studies suggest that herbal medicine use is not merely a health behavior, but a culturally embedded practice shaped by indigenous knowledge and community traditions.

Perceptions, Attitudes, and Behavioral Intentions Toward Herbal Medicine

Beyond cultural influence, perceptions and attitudes toward herbal medicine are generally favorable among different populations. Studies consistently show that individuals view herbal remedies as accessible, natural, and relatively safe alternatives to synthetic drugs. For example, Arce et al. (2024) found that herbal medicine use in Metro Cebu is strongly influenced by perceived safety and availability, while Madale and Salic-Hairulla (2024) reported that STEM students demonstrated positive attitudes toward herbal plants due to familiarity and perceived effectiveness. International findings support this trend. Alotaibi and Rahman (2021) observed that Saudi respondents generally held positive attitudes toward herbal medicine, although concerns about safety and proper usage persisted. These behavioral patterns can be better understood through Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior, which explains that attitudes, social influences, and perceived control shape health-related decisions. Complementarily, Bandura's (1986) Social Cognitive Theory highlights that observational learning and environmental exposure significantly influence individuals' adoption of health practices such as herbal medicine use. Overall, these studies indicate that positive perceptions are driven not only by cultural familiarity but also by social and cognitive factors influencing health behavior. Safety Concerns, Scientific Evidence, and Institutional Regulation Despite generally positive perceptions, several studies highlight concerns regarding safety, standardization, and scientific validation of herbal medicine. Flores-Genuino et al. (2020) emphasized that many herbal medicine studies in the Philippines suffer from incomplete reporting and lack of methodological rigor, which limits the reliability of findings. This concern is addressed in part by institutional efforts. The Department of Health (2023), PITAHC (2023), and the DOST-PCHR provide official guidelines and approved lists of herbal medicines to

promote safe usage and evidence-based practice. Maramba-Lazarte (2020) further argues that while herbal medicine has strong potential for integration into the Philippine healthcare system, stronger regulation and scientific validation are necessary to ensure safety and efficacy. These findings collectively suggest a tension between widespread public acceptance and the need for stronger scientific and regulatory frameworks.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a research design approach, incorporating both descriptive and comparative research designs. The descriptive design was used to determine the students' perceptions and experiences regarding the use of herbal medicine. Meanwhile, the comparative design allowed the researchers to compare these variables across different groups of students, enabling the identification of differences and similarities in their knowledge and usage patterns.

Sampling Design

The study used Stratified Random Sampling. In this method, the population was divided into strata based on strand and section, and respondents are randomly selected from each stratum proportionally to its population size.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Mindanao State University – Sulu Senior High School located at Capitol Site, Patikul Sulu.

Research Participants

The respondents of the study are Grade 11 students enrolled in the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics and General Academic Strand of Mindanao State University – Sulu Senior High School. The total population consists of 261 students across seven sections, using SurveyMonkey Calculator, 155 students were selected.

Research Instrument

The instrument consisted of three parts. The first part gathered demographic information, including age, gender, and academic strand, to provide a clear understanding of the participants. The second part listed 10 commonly used herbal medicines recognized in the Philippines, where students indicated which herbs they were familiar with or had used. The third part included 27 statements measuring students' knowledge and awareness of herbal medicines, with responses recorded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree.

Data Gathering Procedure

Upon receiving approval from the school administration, the researchers distributed the survey questionnaires to the selected respondents during their vacant or free periods to minimize disruption to class activities. Respondents were guided on how to complete the questionnaire and given sufficient time to provide their answers. The completed questionnaires were collected immediately to ensure a high retrieval rate. The gathered data was tallied, summarized, and encoded for statistical analysis using appropriate methods to address the research questions.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the level of knowledge of the students toward Herbal Medicine?

Table 1: Knowledge of the Students Towards Herbal Medicine

	Statements	Mean	Description
1.	I am aware that is harm in trying herbal products.	3.54	High
2.	I am aware that some herbal products may have side effects.	3.65	High
3.	I am aware that some herbal products may interact with other medications	3.68	High
4.	I know that some herbal products can be dangerous, especially if taken in high doses	3.65	High

5.	I know that when using herbal products, you need to be concerned about overdosing or taking too much.	3.89	High
6.	I know that is better to consult a healthcare provider before.	3.87	High
7.	know that should inform my physician of any herbal products that I am taking.	3.88	High
8.	As far as I know, the government regulates herbal remedies to make sure that they are safe.	3.88	High
9.	I understand what is meant by "No Approved Therapeutic Claim" on the labels of herbal products.	3.63	High
10.	Herbal medicines are good for people's health and well-being.	3.97	High
11.	Herbal products tend to be less expensive than conventional medicine.	3.99	High
12.	Herbal Medicine are safer than conventional medicine.	3.74	High
13.	Herbal Medicine are more effective than conventional medicine.	3.59	High
14.	It is now dangerous to take herbal medicine with other prescription drugs	3.43	High
15.	Herbal products are only appropriate for treating minor conditions such as a cold or stomachache.	3.41	High
16.	Herbal products should not be used to treat serious health conditions such as heart diseases and cancer.	3.45	High
17.	There is a lot of misinformation about herbal diseases and cancer.	3.59	High
18.	Health claims on the labels of my herbal products are exaggerated or unproven.	3.40	High
19.	There is not enough information regarding the efficacy and safety of herbal medicines.	3.60	High
20.	I personally used herbal products as herbal medicine.	3.52	High
21.	I have recommended the use of herbal medicine.	3.49	High
22.	I believe herbal medicines are effective even without a doctor's advice.	3.24	High
23.	I believe that herbal medicines are effective.	3.74	High
24.	I observed any types of side effect after I used herbal medicines.	3.54	High
25.	I preferred herbal medicine to conventional western medicine.	3.47	High
26.	I preferred herbal medicine to conventional western medicine.	3.52	High
27.	I wish to know more about these herbal products.	4.05	High
Over-all Mean		3.63	High Knowledge

Table 1 presents the students' knowledge regarding herbal products based on their weighted mean scores. The Grand Weighted Mean of 3.64 (High) indicates that students generally possess a high level of knowledge about herbal medicines, including awareness of their benefits, risks, and the importance of safe and responsible use. The item with the highest mean score is Item 27, "I wish to know more about these herbal products" (WM = 4.05, High), indicating a strong interest among students in further learning about herbal medicines. This is followed by Item 11, "Herbal products tend to be less expensive than conventional medicine" (WM = 3.99, High), and Item 10, "Generally speaking, herbal medicines are good for people's health and well-being" (WM = 3.97, High), reflecting positive perceptions regarding affordability and health benefits. Then items 6 (WM = 3.87, High) and Item 7 (WM = 3.88, High), expressing professional service-related advice awareness. Item 5, (WM = 3.89, High) which suggests an awareness about the dosage and safety. Follow next are Items 3 and 4, "I know that some herbal products may interfere with other drugs" (WM = 3.68, High) and "I'm aware that some herbal products can be risky particularly if you take a large amount of them" (WM = 3.65, High), showing knowledge about risk and drug interactions. Item 2, "I know that some natural products may cause side effects" (WM = 3.65, High) and Item 8, "To the best of my

knowledge, the government does regulate herbal products to ensure that they are safe" (WM = 3.74, High), yet again suggesting a level of knowledge of safety and regulation. Items 12 and 13, "Herbal medicines are safer than conventional medicine" (WM = 3.74, High) and "Herbal medicines are more effective than conventional medicine" (WM = 3.59, High), represent somewhat favorable but reserved attitudes. Items indicating recognition of the limitations are Items 9 'I know what is meant with the "No Approved Therapeutic Claim" on the labels of herbal products' (WM = 3.63, High), 17 'There is a lot of misinformation in relation to herbal medicines and diseases like cancer' (WM = 3.59, High), and 19 'There is a lack of information about the effectiveness and safety of herbal medicines' (WM = 3.60, High). DItems 1 and 14, "I know there is risk in taking herbal products" (WM = 3.54, Moderate to high) and "It's now risky to use herbal medicine and prescription drugs together" (WM = 3.43, High), predict risk awareness but their predictive results were slightly weaker to those of other factors. Items 20 and 24, "I used herbal products as herbal medicine" (WM = 3.52, High) and "I saw some kinds of side effects after I took the herbal medicine" (WM = 3.54, High), represent actual engagement with herbal products and understanding of potential adverse effects. Items 21, 25, and 26 (i.e., "I have recommended the use of herbal medicine" (WM = 3.49, High), "I like herbal medicine more than traditional western medicine" (WM = 3.47, High), and "I talked about my herbal preparations with my physician" (WM = 3.52, High)) reveal reasonable personal usage and inclination but with deference to professional advice. The lowest means are attained in Items 15 and 16, "Herbal products are only suitable for treating mild conditions like a common cold or stomachache" (WM = 3.41, High) and "Herbal products should not be used to treat life-threatening illnesses such as heart disease and cancer" (WM = 3.45, High), indicating a slightly lower level of agreement but still very high. These results agree with studies conducted in the Philippines.

Research Question 1: What is the commonly used Herbal Medicine?

Table 2: Commonly Used Herbal Medicine

Items	Frequency	Percentage
Akapulko	18	11.6%
Bawang	37	23.9%
Ampalaya	35	22.6%
Psidium Guava	41	26.8%
Bluemea Balsamifera	35	22.6%
Carmona Retusa	17	11.0%
Mentha Arvensis	9	5.8%
Niyog-Niyogan	24	15.5%
Peperomia Pepellucidar	13	8.4
Vitex Negundo	60	38.7

Table 2 presents that Lagundi (Vitex Negundo) is the most popular herbal medicine among the respondents at 38.7% for using it as a 1st line herb remedy. Following lagundi is guava makes 26.8%. Overall, the findings suggest that students tend to use herbal medicines that are familiar, easily accessible, and relevant to their common health needs. According to Meñiza et al. (2024), herbs with broader applications and household recognition are more likely to be adopted, whereas those with specific or less frequently encountered uses demonstrate lower utilization. These results emphasize the influence of both cultural knowledge and practical utility in shaping students' choices regarding herbal medicine.

Research Question 3: Is there a significant difference in the student's level of knowledge in herbal medicine when grouped according to sex, age and strand?

Table 3: Student's Level of Proficiency in Technology when Grouped According to Sex

Variable	Sex	Mean Rank	t	P-value	Interpretation
Level of Knowledge on Herbal Medicine	Male	81.88	2846	.929	Not Significant
	Female	76.34			

Table 3 presents the Mann-Whitney U test for female and male students' perception on herbal medicine To examine whether perceived herbal medicine was different for female and male students, a Mann-Whitney U test was run and the results were as follows: For the CHM total, the Mean Rank of females

(n = 103) was 76.34 and that of males (n = 52) was 81.88; the U test indicated that the difference was not statistically significant, $U = 2846$, $p = .929$. This is in line with local findings which suggest that even though there are gender differences in health-related behaviors traditionally and herbal medicine perception in Philippines may be more affected in cultural and communal belief than sex in isolation.

Table 4: Student's Level of Knowledge when grouped according to Age

Variable	Age	Mean Rank	t	P-value	Interpretation
Level of Knowledge on Herbal Medicine	15-16 years old	43.25	0..257	.277	Not Significant
	17 to 18 years old	41.80			
	19 years old and above	48.50			

Table 4 presents the Kruskal–Wallis H test was employed to assess if the opinions of herbal medicine varied between the age groups. As for CHM total scores, there was no statistically significant difference between the 15–16 (Mean Rank = 45.70), 17–18 (Mean Rank = 43.70), and 19 and above years old (Mean Rank = 42.50) groups, $U = 0.257$, $p = .277$. These findings indicate that age was not a strong predictor of views about herbal medicine. Hence, the non-significant differences between age groups found in this study can be seen as an indicator of the cultural significance of herbal medicine in Filipino culture, which crosses generational boundaries.

Table 5: Student's Level of Knowledge on Herbal Medicine when grouped according to Socioeconomic

Variable	Strand	Mean Rank	t	P-value	Interpretation
Level of knowledge on Herbal Medicine	STEM	81.5	-.108	.504	Not Significant
	GAS	80.0			

Table 5 presents the Mann–Whitney U test was conducted to compare the perceptions of the STEM students and GAS students on the educational strand. For the CHM total, the STEM students (n = 75) received a Mean Rank of 81.50 in comparison to the Mean Rank of 80.00 of the GAS students for total score; the difference was not significant, $U = 108$, $p = .504$. These findings imply that there is no significant contribution of strand to the perception of herbal medicine. This finding can be contributed to the culture of Philippine senior high school where students from all strands are frequently exposed to similar health-related information at home, media, and local health conduct.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards for research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was recommended and approved by the Research Coordinator of Mindanao State University–Sulu. Participation in the study was voluntary. Respondents were fully informed about the purpose, procedures, and significance of the study, and informed consent was obtained before their participation. They were also informed that they could refuse or withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty or academic consequence. To ensure confidentiality, no identifying information such as names or personal details was collected. All data gathered were encoded, securely stored, and used strictly for academic purposes only. The study adhered to the ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice throughout the research process.

Conclusion

This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of Senior High School students of Mindanao State University–Sulu regarding herbal medicine. Findings showed that students generally have good knowledge and a positive perception of herbal medicine, with guava leaves, lagundi, and ginger as the most used remedies. Results also indicated no significant differences in responses when grouped according to sex, age, and academic strand, suggesting that these factors do not strongly influence students' views and practices. Instead, cultural and family influences play a key role in shaping their understanding of herbal medicine. Overall, the study highlights the continued relevance of herbal medicine among students and supports the need for proper education on its safe and informed use.

Reccomendations

Herbal medicine education may be integrated into relevant subjects at Mindanao State University–Sulu to strengthen students' generally positive knowledge and perceptions. Health education programs should also emphasize the safe and proper use of commonly used medicinal plants such as guava leaves,

lagundi, and ginger. Since no significant differences were found in knowledge, attitudes, and practices when grouped according to sex, age, and academic strand, school-wide interventions may be implemented rather than strand-specific programs. In addition, family and community-based health education should be strengthened, as cultural and familial influence plays a key role in students' practices. Lastly, further studies are recommended in other schools or larger populations to validate and expand the findings of this study.

References

- Adlaon, M. S., & Elandag, M. P. (2022). Knowledge and utilization of traditional medicine among the communities of Bucas Grande Island. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(3). <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/3518>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Alotaibi, M. S., & Rahman, S. (2021). Public knowledge and attitude toward herbal medicine use in Saudi Arabia: A cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 12, Article 707. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.707>
- Andalan, J. R., Mondejar, A. J. S., Sumaya, N. H. N., Guihawan, J. Q., Madamba, M. R. S. B., Tabelin, C. B., & Villacorte-Tabelin, M. (2024). Ethnobotanical survey of medicinal and ritual plants utilized by indigenous communities of Benguet Province, Philippines. *Tropical Medicine and Health*, 52, Article 59. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41182-024-00624-1>
- Arce, M., Lo See, C., & Ecoy, P. (2024). Herbal medicine use in community settings: A study in Metro Cebu, Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Community Health*, 15(3), 102–118.
- Bandura, A. (1986). *Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory*. Prentice Hall.
- Bautista, J. R., & Raval, C. M. (2022). Herbal medicine use and self-medication practices among students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Acta Medica Philippina*, 56(3), 234–240. <https://doi.org/10.47895/amp.v56i3.1234>
- Catublas, H. A. L. (2016). Knowledge, attitudes and practices in the use of herbal medicine: The case of urban and rural mothers in the Philippines. *Mahidol University Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 43(1), 1–15. https://pharmacy.mahidol.ac.th/journal/files/2016-43-1_1.pdf
- Cordero, C. S., Meve, U., & Alejandro, G. J. D. (2022). Ethnobotanical documentation of medicinal plants used by Indigenous Panay Bukidnon in Lambunao, Iloilo, Philippines. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 12, Article 790567. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.790567>
- Cordero, C. S., Meve, U., & Alejandro, G. J. D. (2023). Ethnobotany and diversity of medicinal plants used among rural communities in Mina, Iloilo, Philippines. *Journal of Asia-Pacific Biodiversity*, 16(1), 88–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japb.2022.09.013>
- Department of Health. (2023). *List of approved herbal medicines in the Philippines*. <https://doh.gov.ph>
- Department of Science and Technology–Philippine Council for Health Research and Development. (n.d.). *Lagundi: Anti-cough and anti-asthma herbal medicine*. <https://www.pchr.dost.gov.ph>
- Elicano, M. L. L. (2024). Knowledge, attitude, and practices in complementary and alternative medicine among selected Asian countries: A literature review. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 7(6). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i6-22>
- Flores-Genuino, R. N. S., Batac, M. C. F. R., & Talens, K. M. D. (2020). Assessing quality of reporting of herbal dermatology trials from the Philippines. *Acta Medica Philippina*, 54(1). <https://doi.org/10.47895/amp.v54i1.1105>
- Madale, L., & Salic-Hairulla, R. (2024). Awareness and attitudes toward herbal plants among undergraduate STEM students in the Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Science Education*, 22(1), 33–48.
- Meñiza, J. F., Pasco, M. M., & Alimbon, J. A. (2024). A review of ethnobotanical studies reveals over 500 medicinal plants in Mindanao, Philippines. *Plant Diversity*, 46(5), 551–564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pld.2024.06.001>
- Panergo, J. R. U., de la Cruz, A. O., & Vilorio, R. D. (2024). Indigenous knowledge and ethnobotanical practices in northwestern Cagayan, Philippines. *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences*, 25(3), 185–194.
- Philippine Institute for Development Studies. (2023). *Herbal products and medicinal plant usage in the Philippines*. <https://pids.gov.ph>
- Philippine Institute of Traditional and Alternative Health Care. (2023). *Traditional and alternative health care in the Philippines*. <https://pitahc.gov.ph>
- Ramos, J. C. T., Delos Reyes, M. K. D., & Dalmacio, L. M. (2025). Antibacterial activity of Philippine medicinal plants. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 154(3), 641–653.
- Rosenstock, I. M. (1974). Historical origins of the health belief model. *Health Education Monographs*, 2(4), 328–335. <https://doi.org/10.1177/109019817400200403>

- Rondilla, N. A. O., Rocha, I. C. N., Roque, S. J. R., Baticulon, R. E., & Mejia, E. A. A. (2021). Folk medicine in the Philippines: A phenomenological study. *International Journal of Medical Students*, 9(1), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.5195/ijms.2021.849>
- Teves, R. I. M., Tantengco, O. A. L., Sumatra, R. J. U., Carag, H. M., & Isidro-Lapeña, J. S. (2023). Ethnomedicinal survey of Eskaya traditional healers in Bohol. *Acta Medica Philippina*, 57(3). <https://actamedicaphilippina.upm.edu.ph>
- University of the Philippines Manila. (2024). *4th Philippine herbal medicine summit*. <https://www.upm.edu.ph>
- Venice Anne, D., Santos, R., & Reyes, M. (2025). Senior high school students' perceptions of medicinal herbs. *Philippine Journal of Science and Health*, 18(2), 77–89.